

ERKAKLAR VERBAL MULOQOTIDA BUYRUQ GAPLAR VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI

GULSANAM TO'LANBOYEVA AZIZJON QIZI

Ingliz tili o'qituvchisi

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada erkaklar verbal muloqotining ayrim sintaktik aspektlari, xususan muloqotda buyruqlar gaplardan foydalanishi tahlil etiladi. Buyruq gaplar tahlili va buyruq gaplarga xos bo'lgan so'z va iboralar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Erkaklarning og'zaki muloqotida buyruq maylidan foydalanish o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega. Buyruq maylidagi gaplardan muayyan muloqot maqsadlari mo'ljallangan bo'lib, erkaklarning ta'sir kuchini yanada oshiradi.

- Ko'rsatmalar berish. Erkaklar suhbatdoshiga aniq, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ko'rsatmalar berish va albatta uing ijrosini nazorat qilish uchun imperativ ohangdagi gaplardan foydalanadilar. Bu kabi aniq yondashuv tinglovchining nima qilishi kerak ekanini aniq tushunishini ta'minlaydi. Ko'rsatmalar bir necha turli bo'lishi mumkin. Misol uchun, texnik ko'rsatmalar, ish topshiriqlari, ish jarayonlariga oid.

Turn left at Orchard Street, and then go straight to go to the bank¹. – bankka borish uchun Orchard ko'chasidan chapga burling va keyin to'g'riga yuring.

A: But I don't know the title of the book. I don't know the author's name either.

B: Then, find the book's subject card.²

Alice: Kitobning nomini bilmayman. Muallifini ham.

Bob: Unda, kitob pasportini toping.

To make a cup of coffee:

- **Boil some water**

- **Put some coffee in a cup**

- **Add some water**

- **Drink the coffee.³**

Kofe tayyorlash uchun:

- **Suvni qaynating**

- **Chashkaga biroz qahva soling**

- **Biroz suv quyning**

¹ <https://www.yeuanhvan.com/grammar-topics/1817-unit-21-dialogues-imperatives>

² <https://brainly.ph/question/14458287>

³ <https://www.yeuanhvan.com/grammar-topics/1817-unit-21-dialogues-imperatives>

- Kofeni ichishingiz mumkin.

• Tavsiyalar berish. Buyruq gaplar har doim ham qat'iy buyruq ohangida ultimatum ko'rinishida bo'lmaydi. Ba'zan, ular tavsiya va taklif ko'rinishida ham bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, mahsulot takliflari, ma'lumot almashish, ayirboshlash, biror ish-harakatni tasdiqlash shular jumlasidan.

"Use this brand for better results." – yaxshiroq natija uchun bu brenddan foydalanib ko'ring
"Read this article for more insights." - qo'shimcha ma'lumotga ega bo'lish uchun mana bu maqolani o'qing.

"Visit this website for the best deals." – eng yaxshi kelishuvlar (imkoniyatlar) uchun bu veb-saytga tashrif buyuring.⁴

Erkaklar muloqotida buyruq ohangidagi jumla va gaplardan keng va tez-tez foydalanish, ulardagi qat'iyatlilik va yetakchilikka moyil ekanlarini aks ettiradi. Shuningdek, buyruq mayli so'zlovchining niyat va ohangni talqin qilishda, muloqot ishtirokchilariga rahbarlik qilish, ularga yangiliklarni taklif qilish yoki ma'lum bir yutuqlarga erishganlarni rag'batlantirish uchun ishlatilishi muloqot sifatini yanada oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

- Ellips va qisqartirishlar. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi muloqotlar doim ham oldindan kelishilgan, qoidalar asosida bo'lavermaydi. Ba'zan, tasodifiy kutilmagan holatda ham bo'lishi mumkin. Shunday kezlarda tezroq fikrni ifodalash, vaqtdan yutish, suhbatdoshni vaqtini behuda sarflamaslik uchun ellipsis va qisqartirishlardan keng foydalaniladi.

Ellips - (yunoncha — tushirib qoldirish, yetishmaslik) — nutq yoki matndagi sintaktik qurilma tarkibidan biror unurning tushirib qoldirilishi, sintaktik qurilmaning tarkibiy "etishmovchiligi", "noto'liqligi". Badiiy adabiyotda Ellips ko'pincha dialogik nutqda uchraydi, shuningdek, xalq maqollari, hikmatli so'zlar va frazeologizmlarda keng qo'llanadi. Masalan, birniki — mingga, mingniki — tumanga maqolining to'liq matnmazmunidan ("Bir kishining kasofati ming kishiga tegar, ming kishining kasofati yuz ming kishiga tegar") qaysi so'zlar tushib qolganligi, ya'ni Ellipsga uchraganligini bilib olish qiyin emas. Yaxshilar ko'paysin, yomon qolmasin. Ko'rganni eshitgan yengibdi kabi iboralar ham Ellips natijasi ("Odam" so'zi tushib qolgan)dir.⁵

Ayrim gap bo'laklarining tushib qolishi:

"My car is blue, and my sister's is too." - car, blue so'zlari

"Harry is working this morning, and Martin is this evening." - working so'zi

"Mary told Steve to dress up for the party, and Kevin too." - to dress up for the party jumlasini

"I want to go to the zoo, and my sister wants to as well." - the zoo so'zi

"Greta ate two cupcakes, but I ate three." – cupcakes⁶ so'zlari tushib qolgan. Birinchi misolda ega va ot-kesim, ikkinchi misolda kesim, uchinchi misolda to'ldiruvchi, to'rtinchi misolda esa joy holi tushib qolgan.

Qisqartirishlar. Qisqartirishlar so'zlarni birlashtirish, ayrim harflarni qisqartirish va qisqartirilgan harflarning o'rniga apostrof yoki tutuq belgisi qo'llaniladi. Ushbu amaliyot suhbat ohangini og'zaki muloqot tiliga aylantiradi.

Let's watch the fireworks together.- Keling, muhaklarni birga tomosha qilaylik

You ain't going to like this.- Sizga bu yoqmasa kerak

⁴ <https://www.yeuanhvan.com/grammar-topics/1817-unit-21-dialogues-imperatives>

⁵ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ellips>

⁶ <https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/english/english-grammar/ellipsis/>

Have y'all been to the new car wash yet?- Sizlar mashinani yuvib bo'ldingizmi?

That's because I studied for the test.- Buning sababi men test uchun tayyorlanib o'qigandim.

You'll have to ask your mom.- Siz oyingizdan so'rashingiz mumkin.

Please, don't touch that.- Iltimos. Bunga tegmang.

I won't be able to come that day.⁷- Men o'sha kuni kela olmayman.

Birinchi misolda – *let us*, ikkinchi misolda *are not*, uchinchi misolda *you all*, to'rtinchi misolda *that is*, beshinchi misolda *you will*, oltinchi misolda *do not*, so'nggi misolda esa *will not* qisqartirilgan.

Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ellips va qisqartirishdan foydalanish o'ziga xos bo'lib, alohida xususiyatlarga ega sanaladi. Birinchi jihat norasmiylik sanalib, aynan onlayn platformalarning norasmiy so'zlashuviga xos uslubni yaratishga hissa qo'shadi. Keraksiz so'z va jummalarni qisqartirib, qisqa va lo'nda jumlar yordamida samaradorlik ta'minlanadi.

Shu kabi qimmatli ma'lumotlar bizga ko'plab tilshunos va jamiyatshunos olimlarning ko'p yillik mashaqqatli ilmiy izlanishlari natijasi o'laroq vujudga kelgan. Dunyo miqyosida bir qator olimlar muloqot mavzusini yoritganlar va u izlanishlar asosida bir qancha o'zbek olimlari ham bu sohada o'zlarini sinab ko'rganlar va fanga salmoqli hissa qo'shishgan. Masalan, quyidagi tilshunos olimlar shular jumlasidan.

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